

Theoretical characterisation of Novel HQSANNA Peptide Sequence

**Dr. Mark Christopher Arokiaraj, MDDM.,
Cardiology Practitioner & Reseacher,
36, Montorsier Street, Pondicherry - 605 001
India
christomark@gmail.com
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ProtParam

HQSANNA sequence MC Arokiaraj

User-provided sequence:

10 20 30
HQSANNATQL RDYESASCHR ISTGLIRYTI GID

Model 01 ▾

Structure Assessment

Oligo-State ?

Monomer

GMQE ?

0.62

Template

A0A2T6CL02.1.A Outer membrane protein assembly factor

Seq Identity

70.83%

Coverage

Biounit Oligo State

Monomer

QSQE

-

Method

AlphaFold v2

Seq Similarity

0.51

Coverage

0.73

Range

6-31

Model-Template Alignment

Model_01	HQSANNATQLRDYESASCHRI-STG	24
A0A2T6CL02.1.A	-----NATQLRDYPPFRE--RLYSVG	672
Model_01	L-IRY-TI-GID	33
A0A2T6CL02.1.A	LGLRYQIVG--	682

Ramachandran Plots

General Glycine Proline Pre-Proline A ▼

MolProbity Results

MolProbity Score	0.79
Clash Score	0.00
Ramachandran Favoured	95.83%
Ramachandran Outliers	0.00%
Rotamer Outliers	0.00%
C-Beta Deviations	0
Bad Bonds	0 / 207
☐ Bad Angles	2 / 279 (A13 TYR-A14 GLU), A19 HIS
☐ Cis Non-Proline	1 / 25 (A13 TYR-A14 GLU)

Molecule visualization

Summary of the top 10 models:

Rank	Score
1	-3128.73
2	-2950.35
3	-2941.21
4	-2852.26
5	-2827.11
6	-2732.58
7	-2715.57
8	-2693.57
9	-2274.81
10	-1850.33

Model 1 Model 2 Model 3 Model 4 Model 5
 Model 6 Model 7 Model 8 Model 9 Model 10

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■ Model 1 ■ Model 2 ■ Model 3 ■ Model 4 ■ Model 5
□ Model 6 □ Model 7 □ Model 8 □ Model 9 □ Model 10

Molecule visualization

Binding free energy of complex: **-32.13** (kcal/mol)

Rank	Residue (Rec)	Binding Free Energy
1	☐ A-TYR-42	-4.08
2	☐ A-LEU-52	-2.49
3	☐ A-LEU-8	-1.94
4	☐ A-VAL-40	-1.84
5	☐ A-GLY-27	-1.73
6	☐ A-ASN-46	-1.67
7	☐ A-VAL-10	-1.59
8	☐ A-TYR-30	-1.21
9	☐ A-ALA-28	-1.14
10	☐ A-VAL-54	-1.09
11	☐ A-ASN-50	-0.88
12	☐ A-SER-48	-0.76
13	☐ A-SER-47	-0.74
14	☐ A-TRP-44	-0.69
15	☐ A-VAL-120	-0.54
16	☐ A-LEU-38	-0.48
17	☐ A-GLY-26	-0.46
18	☐ A-LEU-49	-0.3
19	☐ A-TYR-11	-0.24
20	☐ A-ASN-45	-0.23
21	☐ A-THR-21	-0.2
22	☐ A-MET-9	-0.17
23	☐ A-ASP-23	-0.17
24	☐ A-GLY-43	-0.17
25	☐ A-GLU-53	-0.14
26	☐ A-ASP-39	-0.13
27	☐ A-VAL-12	-0.12
28	☐ A-GLN-29	-0.12
29	☐ A-GLU-103	-0.09
30	☐ A-PHE-51	-0.08
31	☐ A-ASP-65	-0.07
32	☐ A-TYR-118	-0.06
33	☐ A-GLU-2	-0.05
34	☐ A-GLU-67	-0.05
35	☐ A-ASN-107	-0.05
36	☐ A-ASP-19	-0.04
37	☐ A-VAL-22	-0.04
38	☐ A-VAL-32	-0.04
39	☐ A-ASP-79	-0.03
40	☐ A-VAL-13	-0.02
41	☐ A-ALA-31	-0.02
42	☐ A-GLU-75	-0.02
43	☐ A-PRO-34	-0.01
44	☐ A-ILE-82	-0.01
45	☐ A-MET-101	-0.01
46	☐ A-ILE-114	-0.01
47	☐ A-PRO-5	0
48	☐ A-VAL-14	0
49	☐ A-GLY-15	0
50	☐ A-SER-33	0

Showing 1 to 50 of 120 rows

50 ▲ rows per page

Rank	Residue (Lig)	Binding Free Energy
1	☐ B-ILE-16	-3.93
2	☐ B-LEU-5	-3.48
3	☐ B-THR-18	-3.08
4	☐ B-TYR-8	-1.59
5	☐ B-LEU-20	-1.34
6	☐ B-CYS-13	-1.12
7	☐ B-THR-3	-1.04
8	☐ B-GLN-4	-0.79
9	☐ B-ALA-2	-0.45
10	☐ B-HIE-14	-0.44
11	☐ B-ARG-15	-0.33
12	☐ B-SER-12	-0.14
13	☐ B-ARG-6	-0.06
14	☐ B-SER-10	-0.05
15	☐ B-ILE-25	-0.05
16	☐ B-GLU-9	-0.04
17	☐ B-THR-24	0.06
18	☐ B-TYR-23	0.07
19	☐ B-ILE-21	0.09
20	☐ B-GLY-19	0.1
21	☐ B-SER-17	0.12
22	☐ B-ALA-11	0.13
23	☐ B-ARG-22	0.21
24	☐ B-GLY-26	0.55
25	☐ B-ASP-7	0.77
26	☐ B-ASN-1	3.99

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